

Barriers and facilitators for PA

Veuillez remplir le questionnaire ci-dessous.

Merci !

The following questions are about physical activity. Physical activity is defined as any movement of the body that creates energy expenditure. It is found in all daily movements such as :

sports fishing household chores hunting dancing gardening diy
and for all non-motorized trips :

walk bike scotter skateboarding

Please read the questions below and choose the most true answer for you recently.

Barriers: How much do the following things prevent you from getting physical activity?

	Almost always	Often	Sometimes	Occasionally	Never
1) 1. I would rather watch television.	<input type="radio"/>				
2) 2. I would rather play video games or use the computer for fun.	<input type="radio"/>				
3) 3. I would rather use my phone.	<input type="radio"/>				
4) 4. Physical activity is too much work.	<input type="radio"/>				
5) 5. My friends do not like physical activity.	<input type="radio"/>				
6) 6. My friends tease me during physical activity.	<input type="radio"/>				
7) 7. There is no place near my home or my school to do physical activity (field, swimming pool, bike path...).	<input type="radio"/>				
8) 8. I don't have the equipment I need for physical activity (shoes, bike, ball, jumping rope, ...).	<input type="radio"/>				
9) 9. There is not a safe place for physical activity.	<input type="radio"/>				

10) Intérêts concurrents

11) Barrières sociales

12) Barrières environnementales

Facilitators:
How much do the following things help you to get physical activity?

	Almost always	Often	Sometimes	Occasionally	Never
13) 1. Family members do physical activity with me.	<input type="radio"/>				
14) 2. I am on a sports team.	<input type="radio"/>				
15) 3. I play with my sibling(s).	<input type="radio"/>				
16) 4. Friends do physical activity with me.	<input type="radio"/>				
17) 5. Parent(s) encourage me to get physical activity.	<input type="radio"/>				
18) 6. Parent(s) provide transportation to get physical activity.	<input type="radio"/>				
19) 7. Parent(s) exercise.	<input type="radio"/>				
20) 8. I have fun during physical activity.	<input type="radio"/>				
21) 9. I am good at physical activity.	<input type="radio"/>				
22) 10. I know that it is good for me, and this motivates me to get physical activity.	<input type="radio"/>				
23) 11. I feel better afterwards, and this motivates me to get physical activity.	<input type="radio"/>				

24) Soutien familial _____

25) Socialisation _____

26) Plaisir _____